

SUPPLEMENTARY Tables for Manuscript:

Scheuren et al., Journal of Neurophysiology - *Priming of the autonomic nervous system after an experimental human pain model*

Supplementary Table S1. Linear mixed effects regression model output

	Condition (Co)		Modality (Mo)		Time (Ti)		Co x Mo		Co x Ti		Mo x Ti		Co x Mo x Ti	
	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
A. Pain Rating	0.876	0.351	0.112	0.738	3.0	0.083	1.977	0.162	2.362	0.127	0.456	0.5	0.241	0.621
B. SSR Amplitude	0.154	0.695	2.272	0.134	6.684	0.011*	0.518	0.473	4.628	0.033*	0.177	0.674	0.161	0.689
C. Background SCL	3.148	0.078	0.287	0.593	0.354	0.554	0.111	0.739	7.015	0.009**	0.048	0.827	0.396	0.530

SSR, sympathetic skin response; SCL, skin conductance level

Supplementary Table S2. Post-hoc analyses

		Control Condition (CTRL)		Experimental Condition (EXP)					
Time	Modality	Mean (SD)	p-value	Mean (SD)	p-value	CTRL vs EXP	Heat vs Pinprick		
							CTRL	EXP	
A. Pain Rating (NRS 0-10)									
PRE	Heat (H)	3.1 (1.2)	ns	3.3 (1.2)	ns	ns	ns	ns	
	Pinprick (P)	3.2 (1.2)		3.0 (0.9)		ns			
POST	Heat (H)	3.2 (1.0)		3.5 (1.3)		ns	ns	ns	ns
	Pinprick (P)	3.3 (1.2)		3.4 (1.1)		ns			
B. SSR Amplitude Hand (µS)									
PRE	Heat (H)	1.2 (1.3)	H PRE>H POST* P PRE>P POST*	1.1 (1.2)	ns	ns	ns	ns	
	Pinprick (P)	1.1 (1.4)		0.9 (1.0)		ns			
POST	Heat (H)	0.7 (0.9)		1.0 (0.8)		ns	ns	ns	ns
	Pinprick (P)	0.7 (0.7)		0.9 (0.9)		ns			
C. Background SCL Hand (µS)									
PRE	Heat (H)	3.4 (1.7)	ns	3.4 (3.1)	ns	ns	ns	ns	
	Pinprick (P)	3.6 (2.1)		2.9 (2.4)		ns			
POST	Heat (H)	2.9 (2.1)		4.5 (4.4)		ns	0.04	ns	ns
	Pinprick (P)	2.5 (1.3)		4.3 (4.3)		ns	0.02		

Pain ratings (A), sympathetic skin response (SSR) amplitudes (B) and background skin conductance level (SCL) (C) are presented as mean and standard deviation (SD) for each timepoint (PRE/POST), modality (heat/pinprick) and condition (control/experimental). Post-hoc comparisons between timepoints with respective significance levels (p-value) are shown for each parameter. NRS, numeric rating scale; ns $p \geq 0.05$; * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$

Supplementary Table S3. Correlation between skin conductance level (SCL) and sympathetic skin responses (SSR) after the experimental heat pain model and after exclusion of outliers

	Control Condition		<i>Outliers removed</i>	Experimental Condition		<i>Outliers removed</i>
	<i>Spearman's rho</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Spearman's rho</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>N</i>
1. Pinprick	0.33	<0.001	0	0.48	<0.001	1
2. Heat	0.014	0.85	3	0.68	<0.001	3

Additional Analyses to assess the effect of the menstrual cycle on pain ratings, SSR amplitudes, and background SCL

Supplementary Table S4.1. Linear mixed effects regression model output – additional analyses with menstrual cycle as a factor

	Condition		Modality		Time		Menstrual Cycle	
	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
A. Pain Rating	0.698	0.405	0.004	0.951	2.081	0.152	0.003	0.957
B. SSR Amplitude	0.076	0.784	1.827	0.179	8.525	0.004	1.472	0.227
C. Background SCL	3.148	0.078	0.287	0.593	0.354	0.554	5.692	0.018

SSR, sympathetic skin response; SCL, skin conductance level

Supplementary Table S4.2. Post-hoc analyses to assess the difference between menstrual phases (follicular vs. luteal) on skin conductance level (SCL) using a Mann-Whitney U-test (uncorrected)

Time	Modality	Control Condition (CTRL)	Experimental Condition (EXP)
		<i>p-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
PRE	Heat	0.515	0.829
	Pinprick	0.146	0.360
POST	Heat	0.965	0.122
	Pinprick	0.515	0.173